

Synthesis, electrochemical and antimicrobial studies of some azomethine derivatives

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Abstract : New series of 2-[[4-substituted phenyl]imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols have been synthesized by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-[phenyldiazenyl]benzaldehyde with substituted aromatic amines. The structures of synthesized azomethines were assigned by elemental analysis, FTIR and ¹H NMR spectral data. The electrochemical behavior of all synthesized compounds was investigated in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide using electrochemical techniques and overall electrode process was found to be diffusion controlled and irreversible in nature. All the synthesized azomethines (1-4) have been evaluated for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhimurium*, *C. albicans*, *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger*.

Keywords : Azomethines, polarography, electrochemical techniques, cyclic voltammetry, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

In azomethine derivatives, the C=N linkage was an essential structural requirement for biological activity^{1,2}. Azomethines have been reported to possess remarkable antibacterial³, antifungal⁴, anticancer⁵, antioxidant⁶, antimycobacterial⁷, antitumor⁸, antiviral⁹, anti HIV¹⁰, herbicidal¹¹ and diuretic¹² activities. The pharmaceutical importance of compounds having an arylazo group has been extensively reported in literature. Due to excellent biological activities exhibited by azo, methoxy and azomethine moieties, present paper emphasize on the synthesis of compounds having all their functionalities simultaneously in one structure. In reference to our interest in the synthetic strategy and electrochemical behavior has been investigated by using polarography, cyclic voltammetry and controlled potential electrolysis.

Experimental

Reagent and material :

All chemicals were obtained from Aldrich Chemical

Co., Germany. KCl (1.0 mol L⁻¹) solution was prepared in distilled water and used as supporting electrolyte. Stock solutions of synthesized 2-[[4-substituted phenyl]imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols (**1-4**) were prepared in *N,N'*-dimethylformamide. Solutions for recording voltammogram were prepared by mixing appropriate volume of stock solution and buffer of varying pH. A series of Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 11.0 were prepared. Readymade precoated TLC silica gel plates from E. Merck, Germany were used for TLC separation. The pH of the buffer was checked using a pH meter (Decibel DB-1011 digital pH meter) combined with a glass calomel electrode.

Apparatus :

A three-electrode system composed of a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as working electrode, saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode were used. The differential pulse polarographic (DPP) measurements were car-

ried out using the ELICO CL362 polarographic analyzer (India) and the drop time of 1 s was electronically controlled. The polarogram was recorded using a potential rate of 100 mV s^{-1} . The solution was purged with pure nitrogen gas for 10 min and the polarograph was recorded at ambient temperature. The voltammetric experiments were performed using an Autolab type II (Eco-Chemie B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) potentiostat-galvanostat with 757 VA computerize software. The utilized electrodes were hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and a graphite rod as an auxiliary electrode. The electrochemical cell was Metrohm 663 VA stand. Controlled potential electrolysis experiments were performed using an Autolab Potentiostat/Galvanostat PGSTAT Metrohm 663VA stand as electrochemical cell, fitted with a PC provided the appropriate GPES 4.2 (General Purpose Electrochemical Software). Coulometric experiments were performed in the potentiostatic mode using a Pt wire, counter electrode and Pt foil with large surface area as working electrode.

Synthetic procedure :

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds (**1-4**) were routinely monitored by TLC and purified by column chromatography using acetone/n-hexane (1 : 3); (2 : 3) as a stationary phase respectively. FT-IR spectra were scanned on Shimadzu prestize-21 instrument in KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 MHz spectrometer in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as an internal standard, chemical shift in ppm (δ). Elemental analysis was performed on carloErba 1108 analyzer.

Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-5-phenyldiazenyl benzaldehyde :

Aniline (3.72 mL) was dissolved in aqueous hydrochloric acid (28 mL 6 N) and mechanically stirred at $0-5^\circ\text{C}$. A cold solution of sodium nitrite (5 g/10 mL water) was added dropwise to the constantly stirred reaction mixture. The diazotized solution was immediately added in small portions of salicylaldehyde (5 mL dissolved in 40 mL 6 N NaOH) with constant stirring at $0-5^\circ\text{C}$. The filtrate under suction was washed with cold water and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, yield 65%, m.p.

127°C ; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3431 (O-H), 3009 (C-H), 2850–2780 (HC=O), 1666 (C=O), 1596 (N=N). Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 69.02; H, 4.46; N, 12.38. Found : C, 69.00; H, 4.42; N, 12.34.

Formation of 2-[(4-phenyl)imino]methyl}-4-phenyldiazenylphenol :

A mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-[phenyldiazenyl]benzaldehyde (**2**) (1.30 g) and aniline (0.46 g) was refluxed for eight hours in DMF (30 mL). The mixture was then cooled in ice bath and the product separated was repeatedly washed with water followed by ethanol and recrystallised from diethyl ether, when azomethine was obtained as light brown crystals. Other azomethines were prepared by the aforementioned procedure. Recrystallisation from diethyl ether yield 75%; m.p. 181°C ; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3557 (O-H), 1614 (C=N), 1608 (N=N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ , ppm : 4.31 (1H, s, OH), 7.3–7.9 (13H, m, Ar-H), 9.17 (1H, s, CH=N). Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}$: C, 75.23; H, 5.65; N, 13.85. Found : C, 75.19; H, 5.63; N, 13.83.

2-[(4-Fluorophenyl)imino]methyl}-4-phenyldiazenylphenol :

Recrystallisation from diethyl ether yield 67%; m.p. 175°C ; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3545 (O-H), 1617 (C=N), 1605 (N=N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ , ppm : 4.62 (1H, s, OH), 7.2–7.5 (12H, m, Ar-H), 9.34 (1H, s, CH=N). Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{FN}_3\text{O}$: C, 71.01; H, 5.02; N, 13.08. Found : C, 70.96; H, 5.00; N, 13.5.

2-[(4-Chlorophenyl)imino]methyl}-4-phenyldiazenylphenol :

Recrystallisation from diethyl ether yield 74%; m.p. 179°C ; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3514 (O-H), 1622 (C=N), 1587 (N=N); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ , ppm : 4.53 (1H, s, OH), 7.3–7.7 (12H, m, Ar-H), 9.47 (1H, s, CH=N). Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$: C, 67.56; H, 4.77; N, 12.44. Found : C, 67.51; H, 4.74; N, 12.41.

2-[(4-Bromophenyl)imino]methyl}-4-phenyldiazenylphenol :

Recrystallisation from diethyl ether yield 72%; m.p. 186°C ; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3523 (O-H), 1626 (C=N), 1586

(N=N); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 4.83 (1H, s, OH), 7.6–7.9 (12H, m, Ar-H), 9.54 (1H, s, CH=N). Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{FN}_3\text{O}$: C, 59.70; H, 4.22; N, 10.99. Found : C, 59.67; H, 4.19; N, 10.97.

Electrochemical procedure :

The differential pulse polarographic studies were carried out using 2.0 mL stock solutions of depolarizer, 1.0 mL of 1 M KCl, and 5.0 mL of appropriate buffer and 2.0 mL of organic solvent (DMF). The influence of several buffers (phosphate, Britton-Robinson and acetate buffer) on the analytical signals was also studied and it was found that the reduction peaks were well defined in BR buffer, so Britton-Robinson buffer was used for maintaining pH. The experiments were carried out to study the influence of different concentrations and different pulse amplitudes on reduction process of synthesized 2-[[4-(4-substituted phenyl)imino]methyl]-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols. For cyclic voltammetric study, 0.02 M stock solution of depolarizer, 6.0 mL of BR buffer (pH 6.4), 1.0 mL of 1 M KCl and 3.0 mL of organic solvent (DMF) were used and examined the effect of different concentrations and scan rates on the electrode process.

Results and discussion

By the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-[phenyldiazenyl]-benzaldehyde with substituted aromatic amines all the 2-[[4-(4-substituted phenyl)imino]methyl]-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols (**1-4**) have been synthesized. The products were obtained in 65–75% yields (Table 1).

Differential pulse polarography :

All synthesized azomethines exhibited two well defined polarographic waves in the pH range 2.5 to 8.8, corresponding to the reduction of two electroactive centers; azo (-N=N-) and azomethine (-CH=N-) respectively, where the azo group (-N=N-) was known to be more easily reduced than azomethine group (-CH=N-). The peak potential shifted towards more negative potential with the rise in pH for all the compounds indicating that protons were involved in electrode process (Fig. 1).

The reversibility^{13,14} of the electrode process was established by recording polarograms at different concen-

Table 1. Physical data of 2-[[4-(4-substituted phenyl)imino]methyl]-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols

Compd.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Molecular weight
1	-H	181	75.23	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}$	303.357
2	-F	175	67.66	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{FN}_3\text{O}$	321.348
3	-Cl	179	74.54	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}$	337.802
4	-Br	186	72.35	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_3\text{O}$	382.253

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_p$ vs pH of 2-[[4-(4-substituted phenyl)imino]methyl]-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols at conc. 2×10^{-3} M.

trations of the 2-[[4-(4-substituted phenyl)imino]methyl]-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols and it was observed that $-E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential with rise in concentration. This behavior clearly indicates towards irreversible nature^{15,16} of the electrode process, which was further confirmed by logarithmic analysis i.e. the slope of the plot of $[-E_{d.e.} \text{ vs } \log(i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ was greater than $59.2/n$ mV.

The number of protons (p) involved in the rate determining step was calculated from the slope of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH. Diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$) and heterogenous rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) values were also calculated from differential pulse polarographic characteristics have been given in Table 2.

Table 2. Differential pulse polarographic characteristics of 2-[(4-substituted)imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols, conc. $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH 2.5

Compd.	R	Peak	$-E_p$ (V)	i_d (μA)	αn_a	I	$\partial E_{1/2}/\partial pH$ (V/pH)	$D_0^{1/2}$ ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	$K_{f,h}^0$ ($cm s^{-1}$)
1	H	1	0.42	2.760	2.11	0.209	0.053	1.7×10^{-4}	2.2×10^{-5}
		2	1.36	2.394	4.71	0.181	0.064	1.4×10^{-4}	2.1×10^{-9}
2	F	1	0.40	3.395	1.69	0.257	0.047	2.1×10^{-4}	1.7×10^{-5}
		2	1.38	2.785	2.07	0.211	0.060	1.7×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-9}
3	Cl	1	0.54	2.650	1.89	0.200	0.044	1.6×10^{-4}	7.9×10^{-5}
		2	1.54	2.281	2.15	0.172	0.045	1.4×10^{-4}	5.2×10^{-9}
4	Br	1	0.78	1.294	1.78	0.098	0.072	1.0×10^{-5}	1.1×10^{-7}
		2	1.58	3.175	3.68	0.240	0.074	1.9×10^{-4}	9.5×10^{-9}

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammogram of 2-[(4-substituted)imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols in BR buffer pH range 2.5–10.0, at hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) exhibited two well defined peaks and a small anodic peak was observed as far positive potential in the reverse scan. The first cathodic peak could be attributed to the reduction of the -N=N-, and second peak attributed to reduction of -CH=N- group. From the cyclic voltammogram the peak potential separation ($\Delta E = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$) was more than 57.0, which implies that the electrode process for -N=N- was irreversible, while another peak (-C=N-) was also irreversible due to the absence of anodic peak. The voltammogram was recorded at various scan rates ranging 100 to 750 mV/s.

The plot of i_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ (v = scan rate) (Fig. 2) was found to be straight line passing through the origin, indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode

Fig. 2. Plots of i_d vs $v^{1/2}$ of 2-[(4-fluoro)imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenol at pH 6.4.

process. The current function ($i_{pc}/v^{1/2}$) for -N=N- group depends on the scan rates. The cathodic peak potentials were found to shift towards more negative potential with increasing scan rates, as expected for irreversible electron transfer. On increasing the concentration of depolarizer, cathodic peak current increases linearly and hence obey Randles-Sevcik equation, which implies that the process was diffusion controlled.

Controlled potential electrolysis and coulometry :

By using controlled potential coulometry, the number of electrons transferred (n), were calculated from the charge consumed by the desired concentration of 2-[(4-substituted)imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols (1-4). The charge consumed was determined in acidic medium. For this purpose 2 mL of $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the electroactive species was placed in the cell and electrolysis was carried out at -1.4 V against Ag/AgCl reference electrode. During the electrolysis, solution were continuously stirred and purged with nitrogen. Number of electrons was calculated using the equation $Q = nFN$, where Q is the charge in coulombs, F is Faraday constant, and N is the number of moles of the substrate. Disappearance of cathodic peak confirmed reduction of C=N bond.

Reduction mechanism :

On the basis of polarography; differential pulse polarography, CV, and coulometry, a mechanism has been postulated for the reduction of 2-[(4-substituted)imino]methyl-4-[phenyldiazenyl]phenols. Azo group was re-

Table 3. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of compounds 1-4

Compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm) ^a			Inhibition zone diameter (mm) ^b		
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhimurium</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1	14	12	7	2	4	5
2	21	24	15	9	7	8
3	23	27	19	14	14	11
4	17	20	13	8	11	6
Chloramphenicol	42	37	44	–	–	–
Fluconazole	–	–	–	25	27	24

^a1000 µg/mL, ^b800 µg/mL.**Scheme 1**

duced in a two electron step to hydrazo derivatives and azomethine group also reduced in a two electron step (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds (1-4) were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against 24 h old cultures of bacterial and fungal pathogens. Antimicrobial activity was determined against microbes namely *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium* bacterial strains and *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus niger* fungal strains using the Disc dif-

fusion assay. For this, a sterile filter paper disc (6 mm) impregnated with fixed doses (1000–800 µg/mL) of the synthesized compounds were placed upon the seeded petridishes. Similar discs were prepared for the standard drugs, chloramphenicol, fluconazole and the solvent control was dimethyl formamide. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C for the bacterial strains and 48 h at 37 °C for the fungal strains. The zone of inhibition observed around the disc after incubation was measured. All of the compounds tested and showed moderate activity. The activity was affected by substituents on the rings. The incorporation of halogen moiety in an unsubstituted ring gradually increased activity. Thus, compound (3) which includes *p*-Cl, C=N and N=N groups showed the highest inhibition. The unsubstituted and a *p*-bromo substituent showed poor antimicrobial activity. The results have been presented in Table 3.

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